

Radiological Evaluation of Giant Cell Tumor of Bone: A Study of Imaging Features, Locations, and Uncommon PresentationsSapna S Patel¹, Saumil Desai², Harikrushna G. Bhatt³, Yash J Desai⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad²Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad³Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad⁴Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, GCRI, Ahmedabad. B.J. Medical College, Ahmedabad

Received: 01-12-2024 / Revised: 21-12-2024 / Accepted: 26-12-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Giant cell tumor of bone (GCTB) is a benign but locally aggressive lesion, typically affecting skeletally mature individuals. While it commonly presents in the epiphysio-metaphyseal regions of long bones, its imaging features, location variability, and potential for aggressive behavior can make diagnosis and management challenging. This study evaluates the radiological characteristics of GCTB using X-ray, CT, and MRI imaging modalities, with a focus on common and uncommon presentations, as well as the differential diagnosis from other benign bone tumors.

Keywords: Giant cell tumor of bone, CT scan, MRI, Radius, Femur.

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Introduction

Giant cell tumor of bone (GCTB) is a rare but significant bone neoplasm that primarily affects individuals between the ages of 20 and 30 years. It is characterized by the presence of numerous multinucleated giant cells resembling osteoclasts, intermixed with spindle-shaped neoplastic cells. GCTBs are typically benign but can be locally aggressive, leading to bone destruction, pathological fractures, and potential recurrences following surgery. The most frequent locations for GCTB include the distal femur, proximal tibia, and distal radius. However, these tumors can present in a wide range of locations and with varying imaging characteristics. The role of imaging in GCTB is crucial for both diagnosis and treatment planning. Radiographs, CT scans, and MRIs provide valuable insights into the tumor's size, location, bone involvement, and possible soft tissue extension.

This study aims to examine the imaging features of GCTB, highlight common and uncommon locations, and assess the differential diagnosis, particularly distinguishing GCTB from other primary benign bone tumors.

Histopathology

Histopathological examination is essential for confirming the diagnosis of GCTB. Typical features include:

- Multinucleated giant cells, ranging from 5 to 100 nuclei with distinct nucleoli.
- Spindle to oval neoplastic cells interspersed with giant cells.
- Vascular spaces within the stroma, often filled with blood.

These findings strongly suggest the presence of GCTB, confirming the diagnosis in all cases included in the study.

Objective

The objectives of this study are:

1. To evaluate the role of CT and MRI in characterizing the imaging features of GCTB.
2. To identify the common and uncommon presentations of GCTB.
3. To document the typical and atypical locations of GCTB.
4. To differentiate GCTB from other primary benign bone tumors.

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted at the Gujarat Cancer and Research Institute (GCRI), Ahmedabad, between June 2022 and May 2023. The study included 39 biopsy-proven cases of GCTB, both treated and untreated. Imaging modalities employed in the study included X-rays, CT scans, and

MRIs (T1W, T2W, PCT1W, and STIR sequences). The inclusion criteria were biopsy-proven GCTB cases, and the exclusion criteria involved cases without histopathological evidence of GCTB.

Imaging Features

1. X-ray Features

- Osteolytic or radiolucent lesion.
- Well-defined, non-sclerotic margins (less than 5% may show sclerosis).
- Eccentric location, although large lesions may make assessment challenging.
- Narrow zone of transition, with a broader transition seen in aggressive cases.
- Absence of surrounding sclerosis in 80-85% of cases.
- Cortical thinning, expansile remodelling, and cortical breakthrough.
- Trabeculation within the lesion, without matrix mineralization.
- Pathological fractures may be present in some cases.
- Periosteal reactions may occasionally be observed.

2. CT Scan Features

- GCTB typically appears as an eccentrically located, solitary lucent bone lesion.
- CT is particularly useful for assessing aggressive features like cortical involvement, pathological fractures, and soft tissue extension.
- Cystic changes and absence of matrix mineralization can be better delineated compared to plain radiographs.

3. MRI Features: MRI provides detailed soft tissue evaluation and helps in assessing the extent of the tumor, including soft tissue extension and marrow involvement.

- **T1W:** Low to intermediate signal intensity in solid components, with a low signal rim.

- **T2W:** Heterogeneous high signal intensity with areas of low signal due to hemosiderin or fibrosis.
- **PCT1W:** Solid components demonstrate post-contrast enhancement.
- MRI may reveal hemorrhagic areas, fluid-fluid levels (suggestive of aneurysmal bone cyst-like changes), surrounding bone marrow edema, and soft tissue extension.

Results

Out of 39 cases included in the study, the following sites were involved:

- **Radius:** 10 cases
- **Femur:** 7 cases
- **Tibia:** 5 cases
- **Metacarpal:** 4 cases
- **Humerus:** 4 cases
- **Vertebrae:** 2 cases
- **SI joint:** 2 cases
- **Ulna:** 1 case
- **Fibula:** 1 case
- **Scapula:** 1 case
- **Ilio-pubic eminence:** 1 case
- **Talus:** 1 case

Uncommon Results

- **Pulmonary Metastasis:** Three cases (7.69%) showed distant pulmonary metastasis, an uncommon but significant finding in GCTB.
- **Pathological Fractures:** Three patients (7.69%) presented with pathological fractures at the site of the tumor.
- **Soft Tissue Components:** Sixteen out of twenty-one MRI patients (76.19%) demonstrated adjacent soft tissue components.
- **Adjacent Joint Involvement:** Six out of twenty-one MRI patients (28.57%) had joint involvement.
- **Atypical Locations:** Several cases were identified in uncommon locations such as the metacarpal bones, scapula, ilio-pubic eminence, talus, and vertebrae.

Figure 1: (from left to right) Anteroposterior radiograph showing large, well-defined, lobulated, expansile lesion with narrow zone of transition is noted involving epi-metaphyseal region of fibula and soap Bubble appearance. MRI (T2W axial) shows fluid-fluid level and (T1W) post contrast enhancement

Figure 2: (from left to right) Anteroposterior radiograph showing large, well-defined, lobulated, expansile lesion with narrow zone of transition is noted involving epi-metaphyseal region of radius. Contrast enhanced CT scan (coronal) showing peripheral post contrast enhancement

Figure 3: Posteroanterior radiograph showing GCT with pathological fracture of surgical neck of humerus.

Figure 4: (from left to right) T1w out-phase MRI and anteroposterior radiograph showing GCT with pathological fracture of supracondylar region.

Figure 5: Anteroposterior radiograph showing GCT of ilio-pubic eminence

Figure 6: Anteroposterior radiograph of right hand showing GCT of 5th Metacarpal bone

Figure 7: (from left to right) Contrast enhanced CT scan (axial view), MRI T2W Fat-suppressed (coronal) and T1W (axial) images showing GCT of L1 vertebrae with a large exophytic soft tissue component

Figure 8: (from left to right) Contrast enhanced CT scan (axial view and coronal view). Known case of GCT with pulmonary metastatic deposits with internal calcification and necrotic areas.

Figure 9: Contrast enhanced CT scan with pulmonary window image. Known case of GCT with tiny pulmonary nodules likely of metastasis.

Discussion

The imaging findings in this study confirm that GCTB can present with a range of radiological features, from typical well-defined lytic lesions to aggressive manifestations with cortical involvement, pathological fractures, and soft tissue extension.

The presence of fluid-fluid levels on MRI may mimic aneurysmal bone cysts, highlighting the importance of a comprehensive imaging approach to differentiate these conditions.

Although GCTB is commonly found in long bones, the study demonstrated its potential to affect unusual locations such as the metacarpals, scapula, and iliac region. Pulmonary metastasis, though rare, remains a concerning complication, emphasizing the need for careful monitoring.

Conclusion

Giant cell tumor of bone remains a benign but locally aggressive tumor with variable radiological manifestations. A combination of X-rays, CT, and MRI provides a comprehensive approach for diagnosing and characterizing the lesion.

Understanding the imaging features of GCTB, particularly in atypical locations and presentations, is essential for accurate diagnosis and management. Regular follow-up imaging is crucial, especially in cases with aggressive features or metastasis.

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